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Removing the Barriers to Education: Disclosing the Voices of 4Ps Beneficiaries from the Lens of the IP Parents

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Abstract

This qualitative phenomenological study purposed to discover how the 4Ps grants benefited IP parents and how it helped remove barriers to education for their children. It aimed to investigate the challenges encountered, their ways of coping, and their insights about the experiences they have encountered. Twenty selected parents whose children were enrolled in Paopao High School (SHS) were involved in this endeavor. Ten female IP 4Ps parents for the individual in-depth interview and another ten female IP 4Ps parents for the focused group discussion. The results of the interview were transcribed and translated to produce core ideas and essential themes. The essential themes revealed the following experiences encountered by the 4Ps beneficiaries, which include the program as beneficial; it has helped a lot in terms of the education of their children and health concerns. For that, they were feeling grateful. They are strictly monitored, which has compelled them to abide by the conditions of the program. Also, they have received negative feedback from non-beneficiaries and worried about their difficult lives without this program. Relating to their coping mechanisms with the experiences they have encountered as IP 4Ps beneficiaries, the following essential themes emerged: follow 4Ps conditionalities to remain as a beneficiary, neglect negative feedback and focus on the future of their children, and support their education. They shared common insights, such as the fact that the program was for financial assistance, an opportunity, and temporary. These stories of IP parents 4Ps beneficiaries shed hope to others that through 4Ps benefits, their children have become motivated and driven to reach their goals. If used and managed properly, little by little education would be the highest priority, and poverty could be alleviated and would no longer be a barrier to education.

Keywords: *guidance and counselling, barriers to education, 4ps beneficiaries, IP parents*

Introduction

In the Philippines, just like other countries, the right to education has been hindered by poverty. Poverty has been one of the significant problems and societal concerns in the country. In a report by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) in 2021, among families, around 3.50 million families, or 13.2 percent, were considered poor. Filipinos continued to suffer from the effects of poverty in the country. Sad to note, most of the problems and difficulties of Filipinos were rooted in poverty. Many families were left deprived of their essential needs, forcing their children to stop going to school and help them with their livelihood (Lluz, 2020).

As everyone can see, poverty has always been considered one of the barriers to education. How much more if they belonged to a cultural minority, the Indigenous People (IP)? Many Indigenous People communities continued to lack access to decent essential social services, such as education. They had limited opportunities to engage in the mainstream economy and suffered social, economic, and political exclusion and marginalization. The participants received a participant number, a guarantee that the information they submitted would be kept private, and assurances that their names would be protected (DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011).

If you look at it, this was not just a Philippine concern. Millions of people worldwide were poor, limiting access to education, which we often took for granted. In many countries worldwide, the fight against poverty has recently featured prominently on the political agenda. Even in Europe, a developing country was not an exception. "Better educational levels help employability, and progress in increasing the employment rate helps to reduce poverty," according to the European Union's (EU) 2020 policy. Thus, education was acknowledged as a fundamental tool to prevent and lift people from poverty (Hofmarcher, 2021).

In the Philippine setting, the government initiated a program called the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program or 4Ps. It was a poverty reduction strategy that provided grants to impoverished households to improve their health, nutrition, and education, particularly for children aged 0-18. It was the Filipino version of the World Bank-funded Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) Program, where low-income families received cash provided that the conditions on health, nutrition, and education were followed (Department of Social Welfare and Development [DSWD], 2020).

Moreover, the Department of Education (DepEd) is one of the partners in implementing the 4Ps. One relevant feature of the program is the provision of an education cash grant of PhP3,000.00 for one school year or ten months at 300/month per child for educational expenses. A maximum of three (3) children per household was allowed (DepEd Memo No.110, 2009).

Paopao High School, where the researcher was teaching, had partnered with the CSWD since 2013. Currently, 347 students enrolled for SY 2022-2023; 255 students were identified as belonging to Indigenous Families, and 235 received 4Ps (Paopao High School Data, 2023). Considering Sitio Paopao, Barangay Sinawal, General Santos City, many families needed more financial resources to send their children to school, even with free education.

According to the data of Paopao High School for the academic year 2022-2023, many school-related expenses discouraged them from sending their children to school; instead, they were forced to send their children to work so that they could support the family or keep the child at home to help with house chores. It resulted in many children not attending school, although they had physical access. To look at it, Paopao High School was situated in the mountainous area of General Santos City, where majority of the learners belonged to the cultural minority.

Several studies of similar conditional cash transfer programs showed increased school attendance and reduced dropout rates among beneficiaries. Studies documented improved educational attainment, health outcomes, and overall family well-being due to these programs (Chaudhury & Okamura, 2018). However, these studies often employed quantitative methodologies and focused on broad, aggregated data.

The experiences of IP parents of 4Ps recipients were not well covered in the literature, despite the 4Ps' well-documented accomplishments. Most existing studies needed to sufficiently capture these parents' unique challenges and perspectives, whose cultural, social, and economic contexts could differ significantly from the general population. Precisely, there needs to be more understanding of how IP parents perceived and navigated the barriers to education posed by poverty and how conditional cash grants impacted their children's daily lives and educational decisions (Diaz, 2021).

Thus, in this context, the researcher was interested in discovering how their experiences as 4Ps beneficiaries improved their lives and their children's lives and alleviated the education barrier after receiving cash grants from the government. It could raise concerns among the study's intended beneficiaries, leading to implications for practice, hence the need to investigate.

Research Questions

The researchers sought answers to the following questions:

1. How do the participants describe their experiences as 4Ps beneficiaries?"
 - 1.1 What do the 4Ps beneficiaries encounter in the experiences?
 - 1.2 How do they cope with these experiences?
 - 1.3 What insights can be shared and learned from their experiences?

Methodology

This research utilized a qualitative research design, which served as a blueprint for exploring the "why" and "how" of human experiences. Non-numerical data, such as interviews, observations, and textual analysis, were employed to develop a detailed understanding of people's perceptions, beliefs, and motivations. The social and cultural context in which these experiences occurred was carefully considered, providing a richer understanding of the underlying reasons for specific occurrences. This approach delved into the subjective world of participants, aiming to grasp their unique perspectives, emotions, and interpretations of phenomena (Creswell, 2014, as cited in Willig & Rogers, 2017).

In addition, qualitative research went beyond mere description; it involved thorough analysis and interpretation of data to uncover the meanings participants attributed to their experiences. Among various qualitative research designs, phenomenology stood out for its focus on exploring lived experiences and their essence across individuals. This study aimed to elucidate phenomenology by investigating how IP 4P parents benefitted from and overcame barriers to education. Phenomenological research methods were pivotal in describing these individuals' lived experiences (Guest et al., 2020).

Following this, Phenomenology was defined as the study of consciousness structures from a first-person perspective, closely aligned with Husserl's approach, which aimed to describe the appearance of things in conscious experience (Husserl, 1962 as cited in Faber, 2017). It further defined phenomenology as the study of human experience and how things present themselves through that experience, using a distinct method to explore the structural aspects of both experience and the objects of experience.

Consequently, phenomenological research entailed a qualitative approach that delved deeply into individuals' experiences to grasp their essence and significance within a specific context. This method aimed to capture the richness of subjective experiences and understand the unique perspectives and meanings individuals attributed to their lived realities. Researchers in phenomenological studies acknowledged the subjective nature of experience, employing methods such as interviews, observations, and textual analysis to uncover complex layers of meaning. This approach facilitated a profound understanding of the phenomenon under study through direct quotes and detailed descriptions of participants' experiences, providing readers with insights into their lived realities (Vagle, 2018).

In addition, phenomenological research emphasized the importance of suspending preconceived notions and approaching the study openly. By embracing phenomenological philosophy, researchers could explore and understand the diverse perspectives and meanings individuals assigned to their experiences, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon (Neubauer, 2019). This qualitative approach was precious for uncovering the essence and meaning of phenomena by examining them through the eyes of those who lived them (Williams, 2021).

Also, Phenomenological research methodologically centered on understanding the lived experiences of individuals within a contextual

framework, enhancing credibility through bracketing—setting aside researcher assumptions to focus purely on the lived experience. This approach provided a unique and valuable means of exploring the essence and significance of phenomena by profoundly engaging with participants' lived experiences (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Therefore, phenomenological research transcended mere quantitative measures, delving into the subjective realm of human experience to uncover the essence of phenomena. It focused on the "lived world," exploring how individuals experienced phenomena daily. Researchers aimed to understand participants' experiences from their perspectives, emphasizing thoughts, emotions, and perceptions within a qualitative framework. In-depth interviews were a primary method used in phenomenological studies, enabling participants to articulate their lived experiences openly. Researchers then meticulously analyzed interview transcripts to identify common themes and patterns, revealing the essence of participants' experiences (Colaizzi, 1978 as cited in Gumarang et al., 2021; Praveena & Sasikumar, 2021).

Thus, in phenomenological research, participants describe their experiences based on their perceptions, often through interviews rather than written accounts. Understanding these lived experiences requires consideration of participants' beliefs and emotions. Bracketing, setting aside preconceived ideas about phenomena, enables researchers to view experiences from the participants' perspectives (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Hence, phenomenological research proved the most suitable methodology for this study, as it aimed to uncover the experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries, explore their coping mechanisms, and extract valuable insights for shared learning.

In this study, the research participants are the selected parents or guardians of Indigenous People (IP) senior high school 4Ps beneficiaries. The inclusion criteria stated that the parents or guardians should be directly involved with the IP 4Ps program and must have been willing to participate in the study. On the other hand, the exclusion criteria for this research included parents or guardians who did not meet the abovementioned criteria, those who could not provide informed consent, and those who could not communicate effectively in the research language. Withdrawal criteria were implemented to allow participants to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or consequences. In this study, if participants decided to withdraw their consent to participate at any point during the research process, they had the right to withdraw at any time.

In the approval and verification of the rigor and appropriateness of the interview guide, the following data collection procedures were used:

First, I prepared the logistical requirements, such as the venue and audio/voice recorder for participant interviews. Next, I obtained ethical approval from the relevant ethics committee of the barangay, the Barangay Social Welfare and Development Office (BSWDO) of Barangay Sinawal, GSC, and the Purok Chairman of Sitio Paopao GSC to ensure that the study followed ethical guidelines and protected the rights and privacy of the participants. Then, I recruited vital informants who were interested in and supportive of the research; these were the parents of the SHS learners at Paopao High School, who were 4Ps beneficiaries. During the initial meeting, I selected the location and time.

The participants were given a copy of the consent form to sign before the interview. It contained the study's aims, methodology, confidentiality, and advantages, as well as my contact information in case of any questions or clarifications about the purpose. The consent form was then retrieved if there were no further queries or clarifications. After that, there was a Participant Agreement Form. It suggested that the participants and the researcher agree on how the interview and transcription procedure should be conducted. The form also asked for their consent to conduct the interview (Sindhuri & Dongre, 2023).

A one-on-one interview with the participants followed. It had been divided into two parts. The initial section would only request information, serving as the foundation for the participants' backgrounds. The second section of the interview comprised questions about their experiences as 4Ps beneficiaries. During the interviews, the researcher used face-to-face interaction to build rapport with the participants and create a comfortable environment for them to share their experiences. The researcher assured the participants they could withdraw from the study without providing a reason and reiterated their consent to be audio-recorded for data collection (Mezmir, 2020).

In addition, to enhance data credibility, the researcher engaged in long-lasting involvement with the participants, creating a friendly and trustful relationship. The participants were given a participant number and told that their names would be safeguarded, along with an assurance that the information they provided would remain secret. The researcher assured the participants that their identities would be kept confidential and that all data would be anonymized in any publications or presentations resulting from the research (Dahal, 2024).

After the interviews, the researcher transcribed the audio recordings as quickly as possible. The transcription was then shown to the participants to ensure the accuracy and dependability of the words. They signed their names beneath the transcription for credibility and validity.

The data analysis process involved three steps. First, it is called analysis, which breaks down a whole into its constituent parts for individual study. Data analysis takes raw data and turns it into information that users can use to make decisions. Finally, data were collected and examined to answer questions, test hypotheses, or disprove theories (Braun & Clarke, 2006 as cited in Castleberry &

Nolen, 2018; Tracy, 2019).

Further, the data were analyzed using interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA) methodologies. The first interview, observation, and document accessed in the study all served as starting points for the research. The first step in an IPA analysis was to immerse oneself in the original data by reading and re-reading participant responses and making notes that reflected the researcher's initial impressions. Second, it involved finding and labeling themes that describe each text portion to reduce the data's detail volume. These titles are conceptual and should express the text's fundamental essence (Alase, 2017). Third, it involved searching for connections across identified themes and clustering them into structured pieces that made sense of the original data. Lastly, the researcher looked for patterns across interviews to integrate themes into an inclusive master list to summarize and understand the phenomenon of interest (Larkin et al., 2019; MacLeod, 2019).

Results

Research Question 1: What are the experiences encountered by the 4Ps beneficiaries?

The following questions were asked during the in-depth interviews:

1. What are the benefits you receive being a 4Ps beneficiary?
2. How do these benefits help your family and your children's schooling?
3. If without the 4Ps cash gift, how is your child? Is he/she in school?
4. What experience/s do you consider the most significant experience being a 4Ps beneficiary?
5. As a beneficiary, how did 4Ps assist you in meeting your children's educational requirements?
6. Do the 4Ps grants help remove the barriers to education of your children? Why do you say that?
7. What specific obstacle to education does it remove? Why do you believe it was removed in light of the 4Ps' advantages?

From the data collected on the experiences of the study participants, the study revealed a number of key themes such as (1) beneficial to grantees (2) feeling grateful (3) monitored strictly (4) negative feedbacks from non-beneficiaries and (5) difficult life without the grants.

Research Question No.2: How do they cope with these experiences?

The following questions were asked during the in-depth interview.

1. How do you describe the 4Ps grants?
2. Before these grants, how did your family manage your finances?
3. With all the experiences that you encountered as 4Ps beneficiary how did you go through with them?
4. Now that you are receiving cash gift, how did your family manage the finances you receive from the 4Ps grants?
5. How did you manage to survive from the experience as a 4Ps beneficiary?
6. Are you satisfied from the cash-gift receive from the government?
7. Do you see hope from your children becoming successful as 4Ps beneficiary?
8. How did you overcome the challenge as 4Ps beneficiary?

From the data collected on the experiences of the study's participants, the following are themes that emerged: (1) follow 4Ps policies (2) neglect negative feedback and (3) support learner's education.

Question No. 3: What are the insights that can be shared and learned from these experiences?

1. What are your insights as a 4Ps beneficiary?
2. What inner motivations that helped you sustained the challenges being a 4Ps beneficiary?
3. What hopes and aspirations can you share to the other parents who are also IP 4Ps beneficiary?
4. What suggestions do you have for other parents who are also beneficiaries of IP 4Ps?

From the data collected on the insights that can be shared and learned from the experiences of the IP parents of 4Ps beneficiaries, the essential themes are defined as (1) 4Ps is financial assistance (2) 4Ps is an opportunity, and (4) 4Ps is temporary.

Based on the responses of the in-depth interview the following data were gathered:

Research question number 1 deals with the experiences encountered by the IP parents of 4Ps beneficiaries. The study revealed several key themes, such as benefits to grantees, feeling grateful, being monitored strictly, negative Feedback from non-beneficiaries, and a complicated life without the grants.

The participants found the 4Ps program beneficial, particularly in assisting with their children's educational needs, enabling them to continue their education. Feelings of gratitude were prevalent among participants, as the program gave them hope and promised a brighter future for their children. The participants also expressed cautiousness due to the strict monitoring of the 4Ps program. They strictly follow all rules governing this type of assistance to avoid terminating their grants. The negative feedback from non-beneficiaries was also a significant concern for the participants as they felt stigmatized as cultural minorities and perceived differential treatment. For participants, life with the 4Ps grants would be easier, given their limited income and inability to adequately provide for their

children's educational needs.

Research question 2 explored how participants coped with their experiences as IP parents of 4Ps beneficiaries. The following themes emerged: following 4Ps policies, neglecting negative Feedback, and supporting learners' education. To cope with their experiences as IP parents of 4Ps beneficiaries, the participants emphasized the importance of faithfully following the 4Ps policies to manage their circumstances effectively. They demonstrated resilience by neglecting negative Feedback and remained steadfast in their commitment to their children's success. Also, despite facing discrimination and marginalization as cultural minorities, participants exhibited a determination to persevere and advocate for their children's future.

Research question number 3 deals with the insights and realizations that can be shared and learned from their experiences. The following themes emerged: 4Ps is financial assistance, 4Ps is an opportunity, and 4Ps is temporary. Participants became thankful for the financial assistance of the 4Ps as it helped them meet their children's educational requirements. The 4PS grant helped remove barriers to education through its financial assistance. It is the government's way of helping unfortunate Filipino households like them so they can send their children to school. For the participants, the 4Ps are an opportunity because their children were allowed to go to school, so they take care of the privilege the government has given them. Though they understand that 4Ps are temporary, when their children reach the age of 18, they will automatically be cut off from the grants. They will also be terminated if they cannot handle the benefits given to them appropriately.

The themes arose from a careful review of the best abilities and skills I could. Part of this purposeful process was to avoid the questions and look for the themes the participants were expressing. The themes reflected in this chapter emerged from their texts.

Discussion

The researcher chose the qualitative research method, particularly phenomenology since her study involved human perceptions based on their experiences. It also aimed to uncover the experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries, explore their coping mechanisms, and extract valuable insights for shared learning (Colaizzi, 1978 as cited in Gumarang et al., 2021, Praveena & Sasikumar, 2021).

Beneficial to Grantees. Based on the emergent theme, the study revealed that the 4Ps program was beneficial because it assisted the participants in meeting the educational requirements of their children, enabling their children to continue with their education. The support provided by the 4Ps grants helped them alleviate the barriers to education – the financial. It gave them hope and it contributed to securing a better future for their children. As a result of these benefits, the participants felt a sense of gratitude towards the program, as it offered much-needed support that they might not otherwise have had access to. This was particularly crucial for families belonging to cultural minorities with limited income, where the grants made a significant difference in their ability to provide for their children's educational needs (Ramos, 2021).

In addition, the 4Ps program proved highly beneficial in removing barriers to education for marginalized communities such as Sitio Paopao, Barangay Sinawal, General Santos City, particularly those belonging to the cultural minorities. According to a study by Sasaki et al., (2019) the program significantly contributed to increasing school attendance and improving academic performance among indigenous children in the Philippines. This is supported by the findings of this study, that 4Ps beneficiaries were more likely to stay in school because they can now afford and had better health and nutrition, ultimately creating a positive impact on their educational outcomes.

Besides, one of the key advantages of the 4Ps program is its focus on addressing the educational needs of these marginalized community. By providing conditional cash transfers to families, the 4Ps program has helped alleviate financial barriers to education, ensuring that children from cultural minorities have access to and can stay in school.

Furthermore, the 4Ps program addresses poverty-related issues that hinder access to education, such as lack of resources for school fees, transportation, and basic school supplies. This is in line with Taguiam (2024) research, which emphasizes the role of 4Ps in reducing financial constraints that prevent children from attending school regularly, thus breaking the cycle of intergenerational poverty.

Overall, the 4Ps program plays a crucial role in promoting educational inclusivity and ensuring that children from cultural minorities have equal opportunities. By addressing the financial insecurities of these cultural minority households, the program has effectively reduced the burden on parents, allowing them to prioritize their children's education without being overwhelmed by economic constraints (Ramos, 2021).

Therefore, this 4Ps program's multifaceted approach to addressing the needs of cultural minority communities has made it a valuable instrument in breaking the barriers to education and empowering marginalized groups. Through its targeted interventions, the program has successfully contributed to improving the educational outcomes and well-being of beneficiaries from cultural minorities, ultimately paving the way for greater inclusivity and equity in Philippine society.

Feeling Grateful. Feeling grateful is evident among the participants. Most parents were thankful because they could now afford to send their children to school with the help of the cash grants. Despite being minorities, they felt that they were not being neglected and were grateful for the opportunity. The program was a huge help to them, as with every payout, they had an adequate budget for food and for

their children's school needs. Also, one thing that makes them grateful is their chance to be educated and learn things through the monthly training conducted, the Family Development Session (DSWD, 2023).

In addition, the participants are feeling grateful for the opportunities provided by the benefits of the program. This is because it aids them in meeting not only their basic needs but also in fulfilling the educational requirements of their children, ensuring a better future for them. The program significantly reduces the financial strain on families, enabling their children to attend school regularly, which would be considerably more challenging without this valuable support. This sense of gratitude is often tied to the prospect of a brighter future for their children. Parents believe that education is a key investment toward providing improved opportunities and achieving higher socioeconomic status in society. The benefits of the program create a positive impact on the overall quality of life for their families (Flores et al., 2019).

The findings from various studies on the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) suggest that beneficiaries generally perceive the program positively and are grateful for the assistance they receive. Specifically, this gratitude arises from the support that helps alleviate financial barriers to education and gives hope to the beneficiaries, contributing to securing a better future for their children. This sense of appreciation is especially significant for families from cultural minorities with limited income, as the grants from the program can make a noticeable difference in their ability to support their children's educational needs (Flores et al., 2019).

The learners express their gratitude for the benefits they receive in various ways. It is manifested through increased motivation: They show their gratitude by being more motivated to attend school and participate in classroom activities. This reflects an appreciation of the opportunity provided by the program to continue their education. Also, Improved Academic Performance: They express their gratitude implicitly by putting more effort into their studies, which can lead to improved academic performance (Flores et al., 2019).

Monitored Strictly. Most of the parents narrated that the implementation of the 4Ps program is strictly monitored. This is in the sense of monitoring the attendance of the learners in school. One of their conditionalities is for their children to attend classes at least 85 percent of the time each month. An agency like DSWD will strictly monitor the parents and learners' responses to the programs. Under the 4Ps, households may enrol up to three schoolchildren to benefit from the program and be provided with educational grants for a maximum of 10 months a year. For elementary students, the educational grant is P300 per month, while junior high and senior high school students receive P500 and P700 a month, respectively. All of these conditionalities they have to follow, for they will be delisted if not (Republic Act No. 11310, 2019).

The strict adherence to conditions by 4Ps beneficiaries is tied to the program's dual objectives of providing immediate financial assistance and promoting long-term human capital development. These conditions include educational attendance, health check-ups and vaccinations, nutrition, and parental education.

For educational attendance, the beneficiaries are typically required to ensure that their children attend school. This condition is based on the understanding that education can break the cycle of poverty by equipping children with knowledge and skills necessary for better future employment opportunities.

Health check-ups and vaccinations as well as nutrition are also part of the conditionalities where the families must avail themselves of health services, such as regular check-ups for pregnant women and vaccinations for young children. Prioritizing health can prevent diseases, lower child and maternal mortality rates, and improve the overall well-being of the family. Also, requiring them to attend nutrition programs or securing nutritious food for children, helping to combat malnutrition and its effects on physical and cognitive development.

On the other hand, parental education is part of the conditions that require parents to attend family development sessions to learn about responsible parenthood, family health, and other relevant topics.

By adhering to these conditions, beneficiaries contribute to the broader goal of socioeconomic improvement. This adherence is closely monitored to ensure that the program's benefits are used effectively and that the investments in health and education translate into tangible improvements in the quality of life for the impoverished families it intends to help. Non-compliance can result in suspension or termination of the assistance, encouraging beneficiaries to comply with the program's requirements (Republic Act 11310, 2019).

Negative Feedback from Non-Beneficiaries. Receiving feedback, whether positive or negative, is a common experience for individuals. For 4Ps beneficiaries receiving negative feedback from non-beneficiaries, can be a challenging and disheartening experience. In this study, the participants were being assailed with negative words due to the benefits given by the government. These words are mostly coming from non-4Ps members. For instance, the members become the burden of the government, relying on financial aid and being belittled for being minorities.

These beneficiaries may already face various challenges in their lives, and negative feedback can add to their feelings of inadequacy or frustration. This negative feedback can be demotivating and may cause them to question their abilities or worth. It is important for non-beneficiaries to approach providing feedback with empathy and understanding, taking into consideration the unique circumstances and challenges faced by 4Ps beneficiaries. Feedback should be given in a constructive and supportive manner, focusing on areas for improvement rather than criticizing the individual. Additionally, it is crucial to provide specific examples and suggestions for improvement, rather than simply pointing out the shortcomings. This will help 4Ps beneficiaries better understand the feedback and

provide them with actionable steps to grow and develop. It is also important for 4Ps beneficiaries receiving negative feedback to approach it with an open mind and a growth mindset. They should try to view the feedback as an opportunity for growth and improvement, rather than taking it personally. Receiving feedback, whether positive or negative, is a valuable opportunity for growth and improvement. Those who can embrace feedback, learn from it, and use it to improve their work or skills are more likely to succeed and thrive in their academic or personal endeavors. It is important for 4Ps beneficiaries to remember that negative feedback does not define their worth or abilities. They should focus on their strengths and continue to strive for personal growth and success (Araos et al, 2022).

Difficult Life Without 4Ps Grant. The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) provides conditional cash grants to help alleviate the needs of poor households in the Philippines and promote social development. Without the grant, beneficiaries of the 4Ps program would face several difficulties. Without the grant, beneficiaries would find it more challenging to meet their educational expenses. This may hinder the children's access to education and limit their opportunities for academic success. Furthermore, without the grant, beneficiaries would face greater financial instability and struggle to meet their daily needs. This could lead to an increase in poverty levels and a further perpetuation of the intergenerational cycle of poverty. Lastly, without the grant, beneficiaries would be less motivated to attend school and engage in class activities (de Jesus & Villanueva, 2023).

Before receiving cash grants from the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps), they would generally need to manage their finances with very limited resources. They would typically rely on informal work, agriculture, or low-income jobs, and might prioritize immediate basic needs such as food and shelter over other expenses such as education and healthcare. Financial decisions would often be made on a day-to-day basis, and in the absence of the grants, families might resort to borrowing money at high interest rates, selling assets, or even pulling children out of school to save on education-related expenses or to have them contribute to the family income. The introduction of 4Ps provides them with conditional cash grants to assist with health, nutrition, and education expenses. This assistance aims to ease their financial burden and encourage investments in human capital, such as keeping children in school. Without the grants, managing finances would be significantly more challenging for these households, possibly leading to tougher choices and sacrifices (de Jesus & Villanueva, 2023; de Jesus & Rivera, 2020).

According to the narratives of the participants, prior to the implementation of the 4Ps program, most of them labeled themselves as the poorest of the poor. Through this program, they can be able to lift up their children by sending them to school. Before this grant, they only relied on farming, having no jobs, living a miserable life, and having very limited resources.

Follow 4Ps Policies. Prior to receiving cash grants from the 4Ps program, beneficiaries likely handled their finances with extreme care due to limited resources. They would have had to juggle meager incomes to cover essential expenses such as food, healthcare, and education. Common strategies might have included prioritizing immediate needs, reducing expenses to the bare minimum, engaging in informal work, borrowing money, or seeking support from extended family and community networks.

Upon becoming 4Ps beneficiaries, recipients must comply with specific conditions to continue receiving assistance. These conditions often include ensuring that children attend school regularly, receive vaccinations, and that the family participates in community health and nutrition programs. Adhering to these conditions not only qualifies them for the grants but also encourages behaviors that contribute to their long-term socio-economic development. The program is designed to address both immediate financial needs through cash assistance and longer-term human capital development by creating incentives for educational attainment and improved health outcomes. By complying with the program's conditions, beneficiaries are taking active steps to prioritize education toward breaking the cycle of poverty for future generations (de Jesus & Villanueva, 2023).

The narratives of the 4Ps beneficiaries revealed that their coping mechanism in the program as being beneficial, being monitored strictly, and feeling grateful is to follow 4Ps policies. They need to abide with the conditionalities or the rules and regulations being implemented by the program. Due to its significance, most of the participants are afraid to lose their membership or grants should they not follow the given policies. Thus, in order for them to be connected, they faithfully adhere to it (Ramos, 2021).

Neglect Negative Feedbacks. The Indigenous People (IP) parents who benefit from the 4Ps program were able to cope with negative feedback by prioritizing their children's education, maintaining a positive outlook, selectively focusing on constructive aspects of their lives, building community, demonstrating cultural resilience, and seeking success stories. By prioritizing education, IP parents invest in their children's future opportunities and success, which motivates them to overlook negative comments. Maintaining a forward-looking perspective helped them focus on long-term goals for their family's well-being. These IP parents also choose to ignore negative remarks and focus on constructive aspects of their lives, such as the benefits of the 4Ps program and their community's support. Building community strengthens bonds within their cultural community, while teaching cultural values and traditions reinforces a sense of identity and belonging (Grundmann et al., 2020).

Seeking success stories from IP learners who became successful inspired and validated their efforts to improve their children's futures. These strategies demonstrate resilience and commitment to their children's advancement, helping them navigate and mitigate the effects of negative feedback encountered in their journey as 4Ps beneficiaries. Also, By ensuring their children attend school regularly, IP parents invest in their children's future and can overlook negative feedback. Emphasizing the importance of education can help build resilience against stigmatization. The grant from the 4Ps program also boosts beneficiaries' interest in attending classes and

participating in educational activities, affirming the value of persistence despite societal negativity (Lluz, 2020).

Support Learner's Education. As to the narratives of the participants, poverty is one of the hindrances to their ability to support their children with their education. Most of the beneficiaries were afraid that when they were removed from the program, they could even experience difficulties in supporting their children. As a coping mechanism for this, they needed to support the education of their children while they were still beneficiaries or members of the program.

The participants expressed the need for support in providing their children with an education, as poverty posed significant barriers (Chikko & Mthembu, 2020). They highlighted the importance of resources and interventions that could alleviate the financial burden and enable them to support their children's education effectively. The participants emphasized the necessity of support to ensure their children receive an education. It is a good thing that the 4Ps program provides cash grants that can help alleviate some of the financial burden faced by these families (Flores et al., 2019). In return, the participants expressed their commitment to ensuring that their children attend school regularly and make the most of the educational opportunities provided to them. They acknowledged the importance of education in breaking the cycle of poverty and expressed their desire for their children to have better opportunities in life. The participants also emphasized the importance of parental involvement in their children's education. They recognized the need to actively engage with their children's schooling, attend parent-teacher meetings, and monitor their progress (Zhang, 2021).

These parents hope that, in the future, they will see their children become successful someday. That all the hardships they encounter will never be in vain, looking at their children achieving their dreams and breaking free from the constraints of poverty. They firmly believe that by supporting their children's education, they are paving the way for a brighter future, not only for their children but also for their families and the community as a whole.

Financial Assistance. Financial assistance is provided by the government to help alleviate poverty and support the education of children in low-income families through the 4Ps program.

According to the narratives of the participants, one of the insights from the experiences they encounter is that the 4Ps program is financial assistance. It is financial assistance since it provides conditional cash grants to the poorest of the poor to improve the health, nutrition, and education of children aged 0–18. Participants narrated that they were the beneficiaries of the program because they are considered poor and cannot send their children to school. They rely so much on farming or low-paying jobs, which are not enough to meet their basic needs and provide quality education for their children. Sometimes, they are forced to engage their children in forced labor and quit education to augment the family's income. This financial assistance provided by the 4Ps program has given them hope and relief from the burdens of poverty.

The 4Ps program has served as a lifeline for these families, allowing them to overcome financial barriers and prioritize their children's education. This is the very reason that their children are still in school because of the financial assistance provided for them. The monthly allowance that their children receive from 4Ps helps them cover the costs of school supplies and other educational expenses. These parents expressed their gratitude for the financial assistance provided by the 4Ps program, as it has enabled them to break free from the cycle of poverty and give their children a chance for a better future. Through the 4Ps program, these parents have seen the transformative effect of financial assistance on their children's education (Parreno et al, 2022).

An Opportunity. The 4Ps program is an opportunity for families to break the cycle of poverty and create better opportunities for themselves and their children. In this study, the participants are parents belonging to a cultural minority. Life is difficult for them where the source of income is limited and the opportunities for education are scarce. With the kind of situation they have, they sometimes compromise education for food. They sometimes require their children to work to meet family needs. Despite the fact that they understand the value of education, they seem to have no choice but to engage their children in forced labor. For them, poverty—the lack of financial freedom is the barrier to education. But, with 4Ps, it gives them hope. They see hope for a brighter future. The 4Ps program provided them with the opportunity to prioritize education for their children by alleviating some of their financial burdens. Also, they saw that through the 4Ps program, their children could have a chance to escape poverty and build a better life for themselves. The 4Ps program serves as a lifeline for these families, offering them the chance to overcome the barriers to education posed by poverty and limited resources (de Jesus & Villanueva, 2023).

Temporary. The 4Ps program is temporary. It is not hidden from the participants that this program is temporary. They are fully aware that the benefits they are receiving from 4Ps will come to an end. They know the conditions under which their benefits will be terminated. That is why, before it happens, the program establishes trainings through Family Development Sessions to equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to sustain their livelihoods even after the 4Ps program ends and make themselves prepared for it (Diaz, 2021)

In this study, one of the insights learned by the participants is that this program is temporary. The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program is a good and helpful program, especially in the education of their children. It helped their children to have allowances that they can use to buy supplies, pay other expenses at school and continue with their education; however, they fully understand that it was only up until the age of 18. At that point, they are expected to be able to support themselves and their education expenses independently (Ramos, 2021).

On the other hand, aside from being terminated naturally, there are other reasons why some beneficiaries will be terminated. These reasons could include non-compliance with program guidelines or failure to attend Family Development Sessions. For them, as responsible parents, they don't want to be terminated this way. The termination of benefits serves as a reminder that the 4Ps program is not a permanent solution, but rather a stepping stone towards self-sufficiency and sustainable livelihoods. Despite its temporary nature, the 4Ps program (continues to have a profound impact on the education of children from vulnerable backgrounds, especially for these IP parents (de Jesus & Villanueva, 2023).

Conclusion

Based on the preceding findings, I concluded that as beneficiaries of a government subsidy program like the 4Ps, the participants viewed the program as beneficial. They experienced relief from financial distress due to its cash grants, which helped provide for their immediate and basic needs, mainly by removing barriers to education for their children. The program provided much-needed financial assistance for their children's education, allowing them to send them to School and continue their education, fostering hope for a brighter future.

However, the participants faced challenges. The strict monitoring of the 4Ps program instilled a sense of caution among them but ensured program adherence. Negative feedback from non-beneficiaries affected the participants, highlighting potential issues of cultural bias and unequal treatment. It often triggered feelings of shame and self-pity, belittling their identity as members of a cultural minority. Nevertheless, these experiences enabled them to develop coping strategies to navigate their circumstances.

The participants meticulously followed the program policies, which helped them avoid potential termination and ensured continued benefits. They chose to disregard negativity and focus on their children's academic success. Despite facing discrimination, their determination to secure a better future for their children prevailed. These experiences led to their spiritual and social growth, driven by the thought of reduced poverty and better opportunities.

The program's financial support allowed participants to overcome financial barriers and support their children's education. They viewed the 4Ps program as an opportunity to recognize the privilege of government assistance in furthering their children's education. While acknowledging the program's temporary nature, they understood potential termination due to age restrictions or non-compliance.

Thus, these stories of IP parents of 4Ps beneficiaries can inspire hope in others that, through 4Ps benefits, their children become motivated and driven to reach their goals. If used and managed correctly, education will gradually become the highest priority, and poverty will be alleviated, no longer serving as a barrier to education.

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